

Rural Survey on Organic Farming in India

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ABSTRACT

Organic farming has high demand, on behalf of its health benefits and environmental sustainability. Hence promoting it, is the main aim of this survey. Day by day the climate is deteriorating, and this will create a problem not only for the present generation but also for the future generation. There are various factors in the ecosystem which are interlinked. Deteriorating soils and climate change will affect the whole ecosystem thus adversely disturbing the food chain or food web. Conventional agriculture not only pollutes the environment but also decreases the regeneration of the ecosystem hence to improve the ecology one of the major alternatives is to adopt organic farming.

Keywords: organic farming, agriculture, rural survey, climate, economic.

INTRODUCTION

The inability of Indian agriculture to meet the demand for food in the country during the two-and-half decades immediately after independence had been a matter of concern at those times. The system of our agriculture based on the traditional knowledge and

practices handed down from generation to generation could not produce enough to feed the increasing population. The green revolution fulfilled our aspirations by changing India from a food-importing to a food-exporting nation.

However, the achievement was at the expense

of ecology and the environment and detrimental to the well-being of the people. The agriculture system adopted from the west has started showing increasing unsustainability and once again the need for an appropriate method suitable to our requirements is being felt. The practice of organic farming said to be the best-known alternative to the conventional method, also originated in the west, which suffered from the ill effects of chemical agriculture. However, organic farming is based on similar principles underlying our traditional agriculture.

During the year 2020-21, 9.86 lakh farmers have been brought under Organic Farming. And about 9.48 lakh ha area in India is under organic farming as per the Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers' Welfare. (Narayanan S. *et al.*, 2005).

Organic agriculture aims at human welfare without any harm to the environment, which is the foundation of human life itself. So, there is a need to adopt organic farming and make the farmers aware of its benefits. Adopting organic farming practices will lead to the betterment of Indian agriculture in the following ways: (Narayanan S. *et al.*, 2005).

a) Ecological benefits: Owing to the less use of chemicals, biodiversity will be

protected and there will be less soil, water, and air pollution (as farmers will not burn the crop residue).

b) Economic benefits: Organic products command higher prices from health-conscious buyers, especially from developed countries. So, this promotes more exports with the farmer getting more income. Also, because of less use of chemical fertilizers, the government's urea subsidy bill will decline.

c) Health benefits: Organic foods are safe and healthy and also boost immunity. With increased awareness of organic foods, people are inclining more toward organic products and it is a fact that since the advent of COVID-19, the demand for the organic product has increased in the domestic market.

However, there are certain challenges in the adoption of organic farming. They are as follows: (Narayanan S. *et al.*, 2005)

a) Low Yield: Organic farming yield is lower than conventional chemical-based farming in the starting years (2-3 years).

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b) Attractiveness: The shelf life, colour,

and texture of organically grown fruits /vegetables are less attractive than chemically grown hybrid/ genetically modified varieties. So, unless ordinary customers are made aware of their health benefits they may not buy.

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blog/s/seeing-the-invisible/mandatory-natural-farming-will-starve-india/February 19, 2022, 9:11 AM IST>

c) Recent example: of Sri Lanka, where the government suddenly promoted too much organic farming and banned the import of chemical pesticides

and fertilizers. The country went into a food inflation crisis as the crop yield got reduced and thus impacting the food supply.

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Considering the demand potential for organic products and their numerous advantages, the paper discusses the progress and the present status of organic agriculture in Indian villages. It also states the difficulties farmers are facing in adopting organic farming.

METHODOLOGY

RURAL SURVEY: Data has been collected for the current method of farming and to ascertain why organic farming is not widely adopted.

Uttarakhand

Data of districts collected: Dehradun, Hardwar, Rishikesh, Nainital, Mussoorie

b) Preferred method of farming: Conventional farming. In plains areas, commercial farming is practiced whereas in hilly areas subsistence farming is practiced.

c) Major crop cultivated: Sugarcane, Wheat, Maize, Peas, Tomato, Wheat, Gram pea, etc.

d) Seeds used: Which are given by the government, hybrid seeds or some use self-grown seeds

e) Average rainfall: 1700 mm

f) Soil type: North - Ranges from gravel (debris from glaciers) to stiff clay. South-Brown Forest soil which is rich in organic content.

g) The main source of irrigation: Canals, Springs, Small River tributaries, traditional irrigation canals, and artificial ponds on hilltops.

h) Machinery used: uses a tractor,

harvester, power tiller, pumping sets, irrigation pipe tube, rotavator power thrasher, sprinkle machine, chaff cutter, reaper cultivator, and weeder.

i) Fertilizers used: UREA and DAP, the average cost of Urea is ₹130 per kg

j) Insecticides used: Some use homemade insecticides whereas many farmers use chemical insecticides namely super-killers, start here, vitavax, phoskill.

k) Socioeconomic status: Interior villages have kutcha houses, whereas villages close to towns have pukka houses. There is a toilet in every house and people are using it only. The average monthly income is around 15k-20k.

2) West Bengal

a) Data of districts collected: Howrah, Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri, Hooghly, Murshidabad.

b) Preferred method of farming: Conventional farming: Mostly subsistence farming.

c) Major crop cultivated: Rice is the staple diet of west Bengal, other food crops include Maize, pulses, oil seed, wheat, potato, and vegetables.

d) Average rainfall: Ranges from 200-400 cm.

e) Soil type: Generally Black Soil, Saline Soil, Alkaline Soil. they sow

f) Seeds used: Hybrid / High yielding variety (HYV) seed for cultivation.

g) The main source of irrigation are Rivers, canals, Electric pumps, and Boding.

h) Fertilizers used: DAP, Urea, Potassium, Zinc, NPK

i) Socioeconomic status: Villages have the pukka house, and the average annual income of farmers is about 60-80k.

3) Chhattisgarh

a) Data of districts collected: Raipur, Bijapur, Bilaspur, Raigarh, Baloda Bazar, South Baster, Balarampur.

b) Preferred method of farming: Conventional farming: Mostly subsistence farming.

c) Major crop cultivated: paddy, soybean, moong, gram, maize, jowar, groundnut, wheat

d) Average rainfall: 743 mm

e) Seeds used: hybrid seeds

f) The main source of irrigation: rivers and sprinklers, surface irrigation, drip irrigation, boding

g) Fertilizers used: Urea, anhydrous ammonia, DAP (18-46-0), MOP, Zinc Sulphate Heptahydrate, Zinc Sulphate Monohydrate

h) Socioeconomic status: Villages have

a kutch house and the average annual income of farmers is about 60-80k.

4) Bihar

a) Data of districts collected: Aurangabad, Munger, Muzaffarpur, Begusarai, and Samastipur.

b) Preferred method of farming: Conventional farming: Both commercial and subsistence farming.

c) Major crop cultivated: wheat, paddy, mustard, gram, lentil, red gram, chili, potato, tomato, mango, guava, pea, pointed gourd, bottle gourd, bitter gourd, cabbage, sugarcane, jackfruit, Jamun, lemon, onion, banana, pomegranate, litchi.

d) Average rainfall: Aurangabad (960mm), Munger (1231mm), Begusari (1060 mm), Samastipur (1142 mm).

e) Soil type: Aurangabad (fertile alluvial soil), this is locally known as Kewal, Munger (sandy, clayey and loamy soil,) Muzaffarpur newer alluvium, in Begusari coarse sandy loam, fine sandy, loam, clayey soil, saline calcareous soil, Samastipur (light to clay texture).

f) Seeds used: Hybrid and government seeds or self-grown seeds.

g) The main source of irrigation: rivers, ponds, and tube well.

h) Fertilizers used: DAP, Urea, Potassium,

Zinc, NPK.

i) Insecticides used: SUPER-KILLER, STARHENE, VITAVAX, PHOSKILL [UPL& some locally prepared solutions. {NEEM+BHANG+DHATURA Mix.}

j) Machinery used: Tractor, harvester, power tiller, pumping sets, irrigation pipe tube, rotavator power thrasher, sprinkle machine, chaff cutter, reaper cultivator, weeder.

k) Socioeconomic status: Villages have a kutch house and there are pukka houses in villages adjoining towns. The average annual income of farmers is about 15-18k per month.

5) Uttar Pradesh

a) Data of districts collected: Barbanki & Mahmudabad (Lucknow)

b) Preferred method of farming: Both commercial and subsistence farming.

c) Major crop cultivated: Summer crop- Fruits and Vegetables, Kharif – paddy, Rabi- Wheat.

d) Average rainfall: 500-800 mm

e) Soil type: Generally Black Soil, Saline Soil, Alkaline Soil. they sow

f) Seeds used: Hybrid or seeds given by the government.

- g) Machinery used: Tractor, sprayer, rotavator, khupri, spade, bullocks, plough, power tiller.
- h) The main source of irrigation: Mainly rainfed.
- i) Rivers, canals, Electric pumps, Boding.
- j) Fertilizers used: DAP, urea, mop, can, vermicompost [o.f], cow-dung {o.f}, FYM [o.f]
- k) Insecticides used: Super-Killer, Starthene, Vitavax, Phoskill [UPL] & somelocally prepared solutions.
- l) Socioeconomic status: Villages have a pukka house and the average annual income of farmers is about 8-12k per month.
- 6) Odisha**
- a) Data of districts collected: Baleshwar, Bhadrak, Puri, Bhubaneswar, Cuttack, Sambalpur
- b) Preferred method of farming: Conventional farming. In plains areas, commercial farming is practiced whereas in hilly areas subsistence farming is practiced.
- c) Major crop cultivated: Rice, other crops like jute, oil seeds, pulses, coconut, sugarcane, tea, rubber, cotton, gram, mustard, maize, sesame, ragi, potato, and soybean
- d) Seeds used: Which are given by the government, hybrid seeds.
- e) Average rainfall: 200 mm
- f) Soil type: Mostly alluvial laterite. Red soil is found all over the state.
- g) The main source of irrigation: Wells and Tube wells
- h) Machinery used: uses a tractor, harvester, power tiller, pumping sets, irrigation pipe tube, rotavator power thrasher, sprinkle machine, chaff cutter, reaper cultivator, and weeder.
- i) Fertilizers used: Urea, anhydrous ammonia, DAP (18-46-0), MOP, Zinc Sulphate Heptahydrate, Zinc Sulphate Monohydrate, and other wide range of fertilizers are manufactured here. DAP, neem-coated Urea, MOP, CAN, vermicompost, cow-dung, FYM
- j) Machinery used: Tractor, sprayer, rotavator, khurpi, spade, bullocks, plough, power tiller, etc.
- k) Socioeconomic status: Interior villages have kutcha houses, whereas villages close to towns have pukka houses. Annual income of a farmer is approximately 3lakhs to 4 lakhs.
- 7) Maharashtra**

- a) Data of districts collected: Nagpur and Bhandara
 - b) Preferred method of farming: Conventional farming: Mostly commercial farming.
 - c) Major crop cultivated: Paddy, soyabean, cotton, tur, gram
 - d) Average rainfall: 626mm
 - e) Soil type: Black cotton soil
 - f) Seeds used: Hybrid seeds or seeds given by Maharashtra state seed corporation.
 - g) Machinery used: tractor, harvester, power tiller, rotavators, power thrasher, sprinkle machine, reaper cultivator, weeder
 - h) The main source of irrigation: Ponds, mostly rainfed.
 - i) Fertilizers used: DAP, UREA
 - j) Socioeconomic status: Villages have kutcha houses and the average monthly income of farmers is about 15k – 20k.
- Why these above states have not been able to adopt organic farming?**
- While interacting with the farmers, we came across several reasons why farmers were not adopting organic farming.
- 1) Smallholder farmers are not aware of organic farming. Some were hearing about such type of farming for the first time.
 - 2) Some know about organic farming but not completely. They lack access to the right information.
 - 3) They are reluctant to make the transition to organic farming as they are worried about lower yields in the first 2-3 years.
 - 4) Some know about the benefits of organic farming such as health benefits, ecological benefits, and higher prices in the market. But they don't know about the exact technique of practicing organic farming.
 - 5) Some farmers are doing hybrid farming i.e. they are using homemade manure from cow dung, cow urine, and neem leaves. But they haven't made a transition to organic farming because of lack of knowledge.
 - 6) Lack of timely availability of credit acts as another hindrance. They do not have enough money to buy organic inputs. Moreover, they are comfortable with conventional farming as they are not ready to take a risk with organic farming with limited credit at hand.
 - 7) Some farmers have shown interest in practicing organic farming but according to them, there is a shortage of locally available green manure and organic fertilizers, which hinders them from

making the transition.

8) After apprising them about the benefits of organic farming, they are keen to learn about organic farming techniques and are interested in selling the produce from farm to fork. They want organic farming extension services, awareness about the marketing channels, a guaranteed higher price for their organic produce, and they also need subsidies or availability of formal credit to buy organic inputs that can incentivize them to shift from conventional farming practices.

CONCLUSION

The ill effects of the conventional farming system are felt in India in terms of the unsustainability of agricultural production, environmental degradation, health, etc. Organic agriculture is gaining momentum as an alternative method to the modern system.

India introduced the organic farming policy in 2005, National Programme for Organic Production (NPOP), Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojna (PKVY), and Mission Organic Value Chain Development for Northeastern Regions (MOVCDNER). But it appears that India is lagging far behind in the adoption of organic farming.

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The following are some of the issues, which require attention at the government policy-making levels if we want to lay the spadework for the spread of organic agriculture in the country. (*Narayanan S. et al., 2005*)

1) In India, organic farmers do not receive the benefits of government subsidies as they are targeted at conventional cultivation.

2) Non-existence of marketing channels for organic products. Market

development for organic products is a crucial factor to promote domestic sales.

3) The state-level agricultural extension officials expected to closely work with farmers often have a limited understanding of organic farming approaches.

4) Certification requires extensive documentation. Certification is not farmer-friendly.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop a roadmap that sets the long-term agenda for the adoption of agro ecological approaches across different parts of the country.

1) The existing programs to support organic and natural farming should therefore be scaled up, expanded, and properly funded.

2) Consider mechanisms for incentivizing farmers to adopt agro ecological practices

3) Support farmers during the transition to organic and natural farming through technical and financial support.

4) Help farmers sell organic and natural products by developing value chains, procuring produce, and getting remunerative prices. (*Narayanan S. et al., 2005*).

5) A vigorous campaign to highlight the benefits of organic farming against the conventional system is essential to increase the awareness of the farmers and consumers.

6) Identification of crops for cultivation on organic farms is important. The examples of soybean in Madhya Pradesh and cotton in the rained areas could be kept in view in the process.

The domestic market is growing @ 17% and the projected demand for the organic food market is likely to cross Rs. 87.1 crores by 2021 from Rs. 53.3 crores in 2016 (ASSOCHAM-EY).

<https://www.indianretailer.com/article/whats-hot/trends/Organic-Packaged-Food-Market-to-Cross-871-Million-By-2021-Study.a5973>

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The export market size of organic products has increased by 42% during the current year (2021) compared to last year and the volume of organic products exported from April 2020 to February 2021 is 819250 MT with a value of 948 million (ASSOCHAM-EY)

<https://www.indianretailer.com/article/whats-hot/trends/Organic-Packaged-Food-Market-to-Cross-871-Million-By-2021-Study.a5973>

Therefore, India should leverage the market potential of organic products and consider reorienting its agricultural policies toward the same.

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